

Studies on Some Acenaphthaphenazines

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Several acenaphthaphenazines having substituents either in the benzene ring alone or in both the benzene ring and acenaphthene moiety, have been prepared and their properties studied. Dying shades of some of them have been developed on wool. 3-Iodo-*o*-phenylenediamine has now been prepared.

Some acenaphthaphenazine dyes have been reported earlier^{1a-g}. Insecticidal and bactericidal action of some phenazine compounds have also been observed². The present work was undertaken with the double purpose of preparing acenaphthaphenazine dyes and of studying their microbiological activity. We have prepared thirtythree acenaphthaphenazines of the types,

by the condensation of acenaphthenequinone, its 3-chloro³, 3-bromo-, β -methoxy-, and 3 : 4-dinitro derivative with 3-chloro⁴, 3-bromo⁴, 3-iodo, 4-methoxy⁵, 4 : 5-dimethyl⁶, 4 : 5-dichloro⁷ and 4 : 6-dibromo⁸-*o*-phenylene diamine. The products, in general, are soluble in nitrobenzene and pyridine, moderately soluble in acetic acid and

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TABLE I

Name of Azine <i>Group I</i>	Reactants	Appearance solvent	M.P. °C (yield%)	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ . Shade on wool	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
1. 1-Chloro-AP	A +	Cream needles	309-10	Deep reddish brown	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ Cl	C, 74.7	74.9
	3-chloro-O	Nitrobenzene + benzene	(94)	—		H, 2.9 N, 9.6	3.1 9.7
2. 1 : 9-Dichloro-AP	3-chloro-A +	Lemon yellow needles	273-74	Deep brownish red	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ Cl ₂	N, 8.7	8.7
	3-chloro-O	nitrobenzene	(80)	—			
3. 1-Chloro-9-bromo-AP	3-Bromo-A +	Cream needles	284-85	Deep reddish brown	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ ClBr	N, 7.9	7.6
	3-chloro-O	benzene	(74)	—			
4. 1-Chloro-11-methoxy-AP	β -Methoxy-A +	Pale dirty yellow	201-02	Deep brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	N, 8.7	8.8
	3-chloro-O	needles ethanol	(63)	—			
5. 1-Chloro-8 : 9-dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A +	Dull orange needles	Above	Orange	C ₁₈ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	N, 15.1	14.8
	3-chloro-O	benzene	310 (84)	bright yellow			
<i>Group II</i> 6. 1-Bromo-AP	A +	Shining pale yellow	310-12	Light reddish brown	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ Br	C, 64.5	64.9
	3-bromo-O	needles nitrobenzene	(75)	—		H, 2.5 N, 8.6	2.7 8.4
7. 1-Bromo-9-chloro-AP	3-chloro-A +	Shining light buff	289-91	Deep reddish brown	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ ClBr	N, 7.4	7.6
	3-bromo-O	plates nitrobenzene	(62)	—			
8. 1 : 9-Dibromo-AP	3-Bromo-A +	Cream granules	285-86	Deep reddish brown	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₂ Br ₂	N, 7.1	6.8
	3-bromo-O	benzene	(71)	—			
9. 1-Bromo-11-methoxy-AP	β -Methoxy-A +	Pale yellow wooly	179-80	Deep reddish brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ OBr	N, 7.3	7.7
	3-bromo-O	needles ethyl acetate	(38)	—			
10. 1-Bromo-8 : 9-dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A +	Deep yellow granules	Above	Reddish orange	C ₁₈ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Br	N, 13.6	13.2
	3-bromo-O	Nitrobenzene + benzene.	310(d) (65)	yellow			

O denotes *o*-Phenylenediamine.

A denotes Acenaphthenequinone.

AP denotes Acenaphthaphenazine.

TABLE I—(Contd.)

Name of Azine	Reactants	Appearance solvent	M.P. °C (yield%)	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ . Shade on wool	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
<i>Group III</i>							
11. 1-Iodo-AP	A + 3-iodo-O	Yellow silky needles pyridine	299-300 (75)	Brown —	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₂ I	C, 57.3 H, 2.4 N, 7.1	56.9 2.4 7.4
12. 1-Iodo-9-chloro-AP	3-Chloro-A + 3-iodo-O	Shining cream plates pyridine	281-82 (82)	Deep brown —	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₂ ClI	N, 6.5	6.8
13. 1-Iodo-9-bromo-AP	3-Bromo-A + 3-iodo-O	Cream granules pyridine	284 (80)	Deep brown —	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₂ BrI	N, 6.0	6.1
14. 1-Iodo-11-methoxy-AP	β-Methoxy-A + 3-iodo-O	Lemon yellow granules benzene	181-82 (37)	Deep brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ON ₂ I	N, 6.5	6.8
15. 1-Iodo-8 ; 9-dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A + 3-iodo-O	Dirty chocolate yellow granules nitrobenzene	Above 310 (74)	Brown dirty yellow	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₄ O ₄ I	N, 12.1	11.9
<i>Group IV</i>							
16. 2-Methoxy-AP	A + 4-methoxy-O	Shining pale yellow plates ethanol	196 (92)	Ruby red —	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ON ₂	C, 80.4 H, 4.6 N, 9.7	80.2 4.2 9.9
17. 2-Methoxy-9-chloro-AP	3-Chloro-A + 4-methoxy-O	Pale yellow granules chloroform	264-65 (93)	Blood red —	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	N, 8.9	8.8
18. 2-Methoxy-9-bromo-AP	3-Bromo-A + 4-methoxy-O	Lemon yellow granules pyridine	276-78 (88)	Blood red —	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Br	N, 8.1	7.7
19. 2-Methoxy-8 : 9-dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A + 4-methoxy-O	Deep reddish brown granules CCl ₄ + CHCl ₃	264-66 (88)	Deep red light reddish brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₄	N, 15.2	15.0

TABLE I—(Contd.)

Name of Azine	Reactants	Appearance solvent	M.P.°C (yield%)	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ Shade on wool	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
<i>Group V</i>							
20. 2 : 3-Dimethyl-AP	A + 4 : 5-dimethyl-O	Bright lemon yellow wooly needles benzene	290 (39)	Orange red —	C ₃₀ H ₁₄ N ₂	C, 85.5 H, 5.3 N, 10.1	85.2 5.0 9.9
21. 2 : 3-Dimethyl-9-chloro-AP	3-Chloro-A + 4 : 5-dimethyl-O	Silky faint yellow needles benzene	316 (75)	Deep orange —	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	N, 9.1	8.8
22. 2 : 3-Dimethyl-9-bromo-AP	3-Bromo-A + 4 : 5-dimethyl-O	Wooly cream needles benzene	310 (83)	Deep orange red —	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₂ Br	N, 7.5	7.8
23. 2 : 3-Dimethyl-11-methoxy-AP	β -Methoxy-A + 4 : 5-dimethyl-O	Light yellow needles ethyl acetate	225 (96)	Deep brown —	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ON ₂	N, 8.6	9.0
24. 2 : 3-Dimethyl-8 : 9-dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A + 4 : 5-dimethyl-O	Dull deep red shining needles pyridine	370(d) (75)	Deep reddish orange reddish orange	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄	N, 15.3	15.1
<i>Group VI</i>							
25. 2 : 3-Dichloro-AP	A + 4 : 5-Dichloro-O	Pale yellow granules nitrobenzene	315-17 (75)	Deep reddish orange —	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₂ Cl ₂	C, 66.9 H, 2.3 N, 9.1	66.9 2.5 8.7
26. 2 : 3 : 9-Trichloro-AP	3-Chloro-A + 4 : 5-dichloro-O	Faint cream needles chloroform	300-01 (83)	Deep brown —	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₂ Cl ₃	N, 7.9	7.8
27. 2 : 3-Dichloro-9-Bromo-AP	3-Bromo-A + 4 : 5-dichloro-O	Dirty white granules chloroform	295-97 (87)	Deep brown —	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br	N, 6.8	7.0
28. 2 : 3-Dichloro-8 : 9-dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A + 4 : 5-dichloro-O	Orange brown granules nitrobenzene	370(d) (78)	Deep golden yellow —	C ₁₈ H ₆ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂	N, 13.2	13.6
<i>Group VII</i>							
29. 2 : 4-Dibromo-AP	A + 4 : 6-Dibromo-O	Cream granules benzene	294-95 (60)	Brownish red —	C ₁₈ H ₈ N ₂ Br ₂	C, 52.6 H, 2.3 N, 6.6	52.4 2.0 6.8

TABLE I—(Contd.)

Name of Azine	Reactants	Appearance solvent	M.P.°C (yield%)	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ Shade on wool	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
30. 2 : 4-Dibromo-9- chloro-AP	3-Chloro-A + 4 : 6-dibromo-O	Yellowish cream granules benzene	288-89 (82)	Reddish brown —	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₂ Br ₂ Cl	N, 6.7	6.3
31. 2 : 4 : 9-Tribromo- -AP	3-Bromo-A + 4 : 6-dibromo-O	Light buff granules benzene	279-80 (92)	Reddish brown —	C ₁₈ H ₇ N ₂ Br ₃	N, 6.0	5.7
32. 2 : 4-Dibromo-11- methoxy-AP	β -Methoxy-A + 4 : 6-dibromo-O	Yellow needles nitrobenzene	271-73 (86)	Brownish red —	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Br ₂	N, 6.7	6.3
33. 2 : 4-Dibromo-8 : 9- dinitro-AP	3 : 4-Dinitro-A + 4 : 6-dibromo-O	Brown granules nitrobenzene	325-26 (36)	Deep bright orange red, orange brown	C ₁₈ H ₆ O ₄ N ₄ Br ₂	N, 11.4	11.2

almost insoluble in ethanol and acetone. As the majority of them were of light colour, the dyed shades on wool were developed from only seven of them (serial nos. 5, 10, 15, 19, 24, 28 and 33 of the table). The shades were uniformly developed but were some what lighter than the parent compounds. Other details are given in the table in which the acenaphthaphenazines have been indicated serially and grouped in seven groups depending on the diamine used, to focus the variation of shade with variation of substituents in the acenaphthene moiety.

The present study gives no clue with regard to colour in relation to constitution of acenaphthaphenazines.

3-Iodo-*o*-phenylenediamine was obtained by the reduction of 3-iodo-*o*-dinitrobenzene⁹ by tin and hydrochloric acid. The compound was characterised by the preparation of diacetyl derivative.

The microbiological activity of the acenaphthaphenazines is under study.

EXPERIMENTAL

*3-Iodo-*o*-phenylenediamine*: A mixture of 3-iodo-dinitrobenzene (4 g.), Conc. HCl (18 ml) and granulated tin (6.5 g) was heated on waterbath until the tin dissolved and then for a further 45 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice-cold 6*N* NaOH (100 ml) with stirring and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried (MgSO₄), solvent removed and distilled to give the *diamine*, 144°/5 mm. Yield, 2.3 g, m.p.49°-51°.

On warming with acetic anhydride it readily gave the *diacetyl* derivative as colourless needles, (acetic acid) m. p. 231°. (Found : C, 37.6; H, 3.6; N, 8.3; C₁₀H₁₁O₂N₂I requires C, 37.7; H, 3.5; N, 8.8%)

The acenaphthaphenazines, listed in the table, were obtained by heating equimolecular quantities of the constituents in glacial acetic acid solution for 10 min. when the condensed products separated quickly except in a few cases (serial nos. 4, 9, 14, 16, 19 and 23 of table) where the products were obtained by concentration of the solution.

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